

RAVEN: Measuring Detection Instability in Anti-Virus Engines under Semantics-Preserving Perturbations (Supplementary Material)

A Empirical Analysis: ClamAV

ClamAV Signatures. ClamAV relies on signature-based detection, scanning files against a database of known malware signatures. While ClamAV serves as a transparent, open-source reference point, its signature-based approach represents a fundamental detection layer that remains widely used in commercial AV pipelines. Therefore, our analysis provides broadly applicable insights into real-world detection mechanisms. Figure 1 illustrates three types of signatures: (1) section hash signatures (Hash: FileSize:MalwareName), (2) file hash signatures with the same format, and (3) raw byte-level signatures (MalwareName;Engine;Target;LogicalExpression;Signatures) that match byte sequences based on logical expressions that combine multiple byte-pattern rules.

ClamAV Signatures in Detection. We analyze the effectiveness of different Windows malware signature types in ClamAV by measuring their database distribution and detection performance. We determine signature locations by parsing detection logs and mapping triggered signatures to their corresponding PE file offsets. We aggregate detection events by PE section type to identify the most critical regions for malware identification.

Table 1 shows how each signature type’s prevalence in the database contrasts with its actual detection contribution across 5,000 malware samples from DikeDataset, VT, and SOREL-20M, covering 100 families, as described in Section 4.1.1 of the main paper.

The results reveal a significant imbalance: hash-based signatures dominate the database (92.74% combined) but contribute minimally to detections—section hashes detect only 5.35% of samples despite comprising 74.79% of signatures, while file hashes detect merely 0.12% despite representing 17.95%. Conversely, raw byte-level signatures constitute just 7.26% of the database yet detect 94.54% of malware samples, demonstrating ClamAV’s de facto reliance on byte pattern matching over hash-based detection.

B Empirical Analysis: EMBER & MalConv

We analyze the region-level feature impact of two representative ML-based malware detectors, EMBER and MalConv, across different PE regions. For MalConv, we apply Grad-CAM to estimate region importance at the binary level. We identify the top 10 most influential 1 KB windows and aggregate their positions by PE region. For EMBER, we compute feature importance scores and aggregate them by PE region. Figure 2 in the main paper, the .text section contributes most strongly to MalConv detection (approximately 16k windows), followed by the overlay (approximately 14k) and .rsrc (approximately 6k), indicating that the overlay and .rsrc sections play a substantial role in detection, consistent with our ClamAV analysis (see Figure 2a in the main paper). In contrast, header regions exhibit comparatively low impact. Similarly, for EMBER, section contents account for the largest share of importance (36%),

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34304:dc9724d0b8b949b515fb93ea7b644da9:Win.Adware.
Mplug-2166
```

(a) Section hash signature.

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3d4d66b50ecb9e741e416a2a20e1e5b7:44032:Win.
Ransomware.Agent-9809154-0
```

(b) File hash signature.

```
Win.Dropper.Zbot-7165382-0;Engine:81-255,Target:1;
0&1&2;4d535642564d{2}2e444c4c::i;564235213626{28}0
a00{16}00f0300100fffff08000000010000000200;
a24abca00ecf86469f3302464a80a7ff
```

(c) Raw byte sequence pattern signature.

Figure 1: Examples of ClamAV signatures for each type.

Table 1: ClamAV signature effectiveness: database composition vs. actual malware detection rates across 5,000 samples.

Signature Type	# Signatures	(%)	# Detected	(%)
Section hash	4,135,167	74.79	267	5.35
File hash	992,666	17.95	6	0.12
Raw byte-level	401,218	7.26	4,727	94.54

while header-related features contribute the least (31%) (see Figure 2b in the main paper).

C Adversarial attacks (SOTA approaches)

To enable comparative evaluation in Section 4.2.2 of the main paper, we consider four state-of-the-art (SOTA) AE generation frameworks. We select these frameworks based on their semantics-preserving perturbations, diverse strategies comparable to RAVEN, original designs targeting learning-based detectors (e.g., MalConv, EMBER, MalGraph), and open-source availability.

Gym-Malware (Gym) and MAB-Malware (MAB) adopt reinforcement learning (RL)-based approaches. Gym provides a general RL foundation, while MAB employs a stateless multi-armed bandit strategy for efficiency. Both primarily manipulate layout- and metadata-level features, corresponding to RAVEN’s P_1 – P_6 perturbations. They require the target model to label the original malware as malicious before generating AEs.

Malguise introduces instruction-level control-flow perturbations, such as semantic NOP insertion and call redivision, modifying instruction layout without rewriting the overall CFG. These techniques align with RAVEN’s P_9 , P_{10} , and partially P_{12} . They also depend on prior malicious labeling by the target model.

MalwareMakeover (MMO) performs instruction-level transformations, including DISP, register reassignment, instruction reordering, and equivalent instruction replacement. In this work, we use

Figure 2: Clustering of AV engines under single-perturbation setting, based on FPR and ASR.

Table 2: AV engine groupings corresponding to the clusters in Figure 2.

Group	AV Engines
Robust	Google, Ikarus, Elastic, Cynet, McAfeeD, huorong, Skyhigh, Kingsoft, CrowdStrike, Trapmine, APEX, Cylance, Bkav
Perturbation-Sensitive	Antiy-AVL, ESET-NOD32, Fortinet, ClamAV, Sophos, Malwarebytes, DrWeb, Kaspersky, GData, Symantec, VIPRE, Emsisoft, MicroWorld-eScan, Rising, CTX, K7AntiVirus, BitDefender, VBA32, McAfee, Varist, Microsoft, DeepInstinct, Jiangmin, SentinelOne, Avast, AVG, ALYac, AhnLab-V3, CAT-QuickHeal, Xcitium, TrendMicro-HouseCall, F-Secure, Avira, Zillya, MaxSecure, ZoneAlarm, Yandex, alibabacloud, VirIT, Gridinsoft, Panda, Webroot, TrendMicro, Acronis, Baidu, TACHYON, tehtris, ViRobot, SUPERAntiSpyware, Zoner, CMC
Oversensitive	Alibaba, Lionic, Paloalto

only its perturbation components. These components span both control-flow and resource/section-level modifications corresponding to RAVEN’s P_9 , P_{10} , and P_{12} . Unlike the RL-based frameworks, MMO does not require prior malicious classification.

Unlike prior optimization-centric frameworks, we treat generated AEs as independent inputs. We use them to measure longitudinal detection instability across the AV ecosystem rather than to optimize evasion performance.

D AV Detection Strategy Taxonomy via Behavioral Clustering

Figure 2 illustrates the clustering of AV engines based on their FPR and ASR. The analysis uses VT reports from 5,000 randomly sampled AE-OG pairs, drawn from a larger pool in Section 4.2.1 of

Figure 3: K-Means clustering ($k=3$) of AV engines based on their ASR and FPR in RQ3 of the main paper.

Table 3: AV engine list corresponding to the clusters shown in Figure 3.

Group	AV Engines
Robust	Google, Elastic, McAfeeD, Cynet, Cylance, Skyhigh, CrowdStrike, Kingsoft, APEX, Bkav, Trapmine
Perturbation-Sensitive	Symantec, ClamAV, Antiy-AVL, TrendMicro-HouseCall, Malwarebytes, VIPRE, DeepInstinct, Sophos, Emsisoft, MicroWorld-eScan, GData, Arcabit, CTX, BitDefender, Sangfor, Rising, Avast, AVG, ALYac, Microsoft, SentinelOne, Avira, F-Secure, Ikarus, MaxSecure, huorong
Oversensitive	Lionic, Tencent, ESET-NOD32, Fortinet, Kaspersky, K7AntiVirus, CAT-QuickHeal, K7GW, VBA32, DrWeb, AhnLab-V3, Varist, NANO-Antivirus, Zillya, Alibaba, Paloalto, Jiangmin, Xcitium, alibabacloud, Panda, ZoneAlarm, TrendMicro, VirIT, Gridinsoft, Yandex, Webroot, Acronis, ViRobot, TACHYON, tehtris, Baidu, SUPERAntiSpyware, Zoner, CMC

the main paper to avoid selection bias, along with a separate set of benign files. We compute ASR only for AV engines that appear in both the original malware and AE reports of each pair, while we derive FPR from benign reports. We exclude AV engines that do not appear in either dataset.

The clustering reveals three distinct behavioral groups: (1) **Robust** engines (green) maintain low ASR while tolerating moderate FPR; (2) **Oversensitive** engines (red) show extremely low FPR but fail to detect most AE; and (3) **Perturbation-Sensitive** engines (blue) achieve low FPR but suffer from high ASR, indicating vulnerability to structural perturbations. Table 2 lists the AV engines assigned to each behavioral category.

Table 4: Summary of representative AE generation methods for Windows PE binaries, categorized by perturbation strategy, VT evaluation setting, and perturbation count.

Method	Perturbation Strategy	Perturbation Type	VT Evaluation	# Perturbations
ARMED	Heuristic byte mutation	Byte-level	Yes (Longitudinal)	9
AIMED	Genetic byte mutation	Byte-level	No	9
GAMBD	RL-guided byte editing	Byte-level	Yes (Single-shot)	1
RAMEn	PE header/section editing	PE-structure	Yes (Single-shot)	3
FUMVar	Evolutionary PE field changes	PE-structure	Yes (Single-shot)	13
GAMMA	Genetic section mutation	PE-structure	Yes (Single-shot)	8
AMG-VAC	RL on static PE features	PE-structure	No	10
MAB-Malware	Multi-armed bandit PE edits	PE-structure	No	13
PSP-Mal	SHAP-prioritized PE mutation via RL	PE-structure	No	10
Gym-Malware	DQN-based PE perturbation	PE-structure	Yes (Single-shot)	9
MalwareMakeover	Instruction-level semantic edits	Code semantics	Yes (Single-shot)	6
MalwareTotal	PPO-RL over PE and metadata	PE structure + metadata	Yes (Single-shot)	23
Malguise	CFG obfuscation via MCTS	Control-flow	No	2
Zhang et al	semantic NOP insertion via symbolic control-flow analysis	Control-flow	No	1
MalFox	GAN-based behavior camouflage	Obfuscation (semantic)	Yes (Single-shot)	3
MEME	RL with surrogate model + API-level mimicry	PE structure + behavior	No	15

E Clustering Engines based on ASR and FPR in RQ3 of the Main Paper.

We evaluate AV robustness using AEs generated with the most evasive configuration (PSC+IC+JOB+CS). To compute ASR, we pair each AE with its original malware and count cases where the AV engine misses the AE despite detecting the original sample. We also compute each engine’s FPR and ASR using both benign and malicious reports. We use benign reports to compute FPR, while we use original malware and AE reports to determine true positives, false negatives, and ASR components. We exclude engines with insufficient scan coverage, as sparse participation could lead to unstable or misleading evaluation metrics. Figure 3 shows K-Means clustering ($k=3$) based on standardized ASR and FPR, and Table 3 lists engines by cluster. Colors represent three behaviorally distinct groups.

F AE Generation Methods

Table 4 summarizes representative AE generation methods for Windows PE binaries evaluated in prior work, categorized by perturbation strategy, evaluation setting, and perturbation count. These approaches vary in how they modify binaries, ranging from byte-level mutations (e.g., ARMED, GAMBD) to PE-structure edits (e.g., RAMER, FUMVar, MAB-Malware) and semantic transformations (e.g., MalwareMakeover, MEME, Malguise). The number of perturbations also differs significantly across methods, ranging from a single transformation (e.g., GAMBD, Zhang et al.) to as many as 23 in MalwareTotal. Notably, recent methods such as Gym-Malware, MAB-Malware, and Malguise focus on ML-guided or control-flow-aware perturbations and achieve strong performance against ML-based AV engines.